

EXTENT OF AVAILABILITY OF ICT RESOURCES FOR QUALITY ASSURANCE OF BUSINESS EDUCATION IN SOUTH-WEST NIGERIA

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Abstract:

This study aimed at assessing the extent of availability of ICT resources for quality assurance of Business Education in South-West Nigeria. One research question and three null hypotheses were drawn to guide the study. Related literatures were reviewed after the conceptual framework based on the major variables of the study. A Descriptive research design was adopted to conduct the study. The population of the study comprises 550 (52 lecturers and 498 final year students) of Business Education from universities that offer Business Education in South-West Nigeria. A sample size of three hundred and one (301) 52 lecturers and 249 students was used for the study; using stratified random sampling techniques. A modified questionnaire was used for data collection. The reliability of the instrument was established through the use of Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Coefficient and reliability coefficients of 0.87. Arithmetic mean and standard Deviation were used to analyze data and answer research questions. While z-test was used to test hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of this study revealed that ICT resources are available at a low extent for quality assurance of business education in universities in South-West Nigeria. This study recommends, among others, that the Government and managements of programme should join hands together and ensure that ICT resources are available to enhance qualitative teaching and learning of 21st century that afford the students job opportunities in the global labour market.

Keywords: availability, ICT resources, quality assurance, business education

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1. Introduction

The world has turned to be a global village now as a result of Information Communication Technology (ICT). Simply put, we are in the era of information age. These technologies have brought profound changes to all human endeavours. The ease of data collection, processing, transmission, and interpretation provided these technologies have engendered the flow of information across boards and between individuals, cultures, nationalities, corporate bodies and organization as never before, causing great technological, economic and social changes and binding the world ever more closely together. This has made it one of the basic building blocks of modern society. The technological change process has accelerated in tandem to create a new world power based ICT. Hardly could we not talk of involvement of ICT in all sectors of life; be in medicine, business, banking, politics, military, economics, insurance. If all sectors are reformed in terms of ICT, education too should not be left out. It is widely believed that education should now be ICT challenged and biased. Although ICT resources have been looked upon as tools for the upliftment of the standard of education in any nation, the level of compliance in implementing the ICT resources in instructional development process leaves much to be desired in Nigerian higher education system. Recent developments in ICT have drastically affected educational procedure for improved quality of education offered to students. ICT resources in instructional delivery in schools will serve a dual purpose and more efficient classroom instruction (Nzewi, 2009; Umoren, 2006). It is in the pursuance of the need to access international best practices that the Federal government reviewed the National Policy on Education (1998) to the current one (NPE, 2004) to accommodate the introduction of ICT into the school system in keeping with the dynamics of social change and its demand on education.

University education prepares teachers that feed the primary and secondary school levels of education in Nigeria with manpower demands. It is at this level that they should have their first encounter with technology in the classroom, this they will put to use when eventually they leave school and are gainfully employed to teachers in the primary and secondary schools. It is in this light that the training of student teachers, who are expected to drive the new ICT advanced education system, is brought afore. The advancement in which ICT resources offer in higher education, can be evident through accessibility to available quality ICT resources. This can only be attained when it is drastically integrated into the instructional process in the teacher education system. Productive instructional delivery enhances learners' creative and

intellectual development through the use of ICT resources, for instance, in the use of multimedia images, graphics, audio, text and motion for high quality learning.

Business education as an integral part of vocational and technical education is a form of vocational education according to Idialu (2007) that is directed towards developing the learner to become productive in teaching, paid employment and self-employment. Amoor and Udoh (2008) noted that business education plays a significant role in the economic development by providing knowledge and skills to the learners thereby enabling them to adequately impart knowledge into others, and handle sophisticated office technologies and information systems. The goal of business education is primarily to produce competent, skilful and dynamic business teachers, office administrators and businessmen and women that will effectively compete in the world of work. The emergence of Vocational education in the global scene is necessitated by the need to provide the society with a form of education that promotes lifelong learning, needs of the community, innovation, employability and self-reliance (Okorie, 2004). Business education is rooted in Vocational education with specific mandate of providing skills, attitude and knowledge needed for employment or running a business. According to Anao in Oliver (2011), business education is the sum total of the knowledge, skills and attitude that are required for successfully promoting and administering business enterprises. The need for business education as a form of education is crucial especially in this era of globalization and information and communication technology (ICT) in which work processes and organizations are getting increasingly flexible, multi-tasking and performance-base. Murray (2003), posited that economic forecasts and business analysts predict that the 21st century jobs will require information processing skills. Development of information literacy, therefore, becomes inevitable for workers of the future.

Business Education as a programme needs to meet up with the needs of the learner and the society. And if that be the case, assuring quality of what is taught both skills and knowledge is very vital. Quality assurance is a process centered approach to ensuring that organization is providing the best possible products or service. Quality assurance refers to the planned and systematic activities implemented in a quality system so that quality requirements for a product or services will be fulfilled. Idialu (2007) described quality as standards of something as compared to other things, that is, the degree of goodness or excellence. Quality assurance in the context of this study means all the procedures, processes and systems that support and develop business education. If knowledge were stagnant in business education without improvement in what the learner learns in order to be relevant in his society, there would have been total abandonment of the programmes in Business Education since it may appear not to

be providing the needs of the learners and that of the society. But since there is always content improvement through introduction of new technologies and approaches in the method of teaching and in what is learnt, the discipline has always provided for the needs of the society, hence maintaining a high standard in providing manpower for the industries in the economy. It will be pertinent in this regard to generally say that education quality is measured by the usefulness of or the compensation for opportunity cost for learners from the education to achieve learning objectives. The demand of education is based on its ability to provide qualitative marketable skills that will help individuals to engage in meaningful occupation. Business Education having upheld this idea of providing marketable skills to learners has remained relevant in the world of study. Many factors are influencing the effort to make business education relevant today, one of which is the spate of technological advancements being witnessed. Technology has become the nexus of operation in the business world. Consequently, business education is affected in terms of instruction and delivery and in skills and competencies needed to adapt to these evolving technologies used for operation in offices. The technological changes in business education are basically from information and communication technology (ICT) perspective. The society generally is ICT-driven and in order to keep abreast of this change, there must be a restructuring in the knowledge and skills given to learners/students in Business Education. Electronic office (e office) is one of the phenomena of the 21st century which is a paperless office approach in which every office work is done with the use of computer. It is based on this that most Business Education departments across Nigeria's tertiary institutions need to building ICT centers, improved computer laboratories and as well as offering professional courses in computer studies to produce students/graduates that can easily adapt in their ever changing business environment. The use of typewriter is almost going into extinct as the computer is fast taking over. The topic of such as availability and use of ICT resources in Business Education has become imperative because of the fact that these programme would produce teachers that need to teach/educate populace of values of ICT and its integration.

Availability, in the opinion of Ibrahim (2007) refers to the condition of being obtainable or accessible at a particular point in time while in the word of Joshua (2011), availability expresses how a material can easily be gotten and used for a particular purpose and time. According to Bangbelu (2003), availability states how operable or usable resources are upon demand to perform its designated or required functions. Premised on these definitions, availability means the condition with which lecturers have access and make use of ICT resources for qualitative and effective instructional delivery to meet the needs of the society through the students. Availability of suitable

instructional facilities in good supply and in rich variety and range is essential in education and especially for the achievement of curriculum objectives. Teaching is not complete until knowledge has successfully transferred which in most cases depend on the instructional facilities used in the learning process. Ordinary words or verbalization has been found to be inadequate for effective teaching. Instructional facilities such as ICT resources serve as a channel through which message; information, ideas, and knowledge are disseminated more easily and could be turned to for help in learning process. To accomplish this, it must be readily and adequately available. As ICT is being integrated into education in the 21st century, it is expected that teaching and learning can be performed using available ICT facilities to produce quality graduates. Therefore, availability in the context of this study refers to the quality, quantity, functionality and disposability of ICT resources to teachers at every point in time for effective utilization of qualitative instructional delivery.

Gender is a factor that may determine the outcome of this study. Gender is the sexual characteristics designated to a person by the environment. Abul (2007) refers to gender as the socially defined capabilities and attributes assigned to persons on the basis of their alleged sexual characteristics. Similarly, Adesope, Asiabaka, and Agumagu (2009) explained that gender is the roles, attitudes, behaviour and values ascribe by the society to male and female. In the past, there has been a general view supported by research that male student perform better than female in practical oriented courses. For instance, Anigbogu (2002) pointed out that some cultures see male more superior to female and that such feelings is manifested in every aspect of their lives. Supporting this view, Onyemelukwe (2005) explained that men use internet and other ICT resources than women. In contrast, Koko (2005) opines that male students experience less anxiety than female students.

Status is another factor that may determine the availability of ICT resources in universities in Nigeria. According to Salami (2013), status is the position or rank of someone or something when compared to others in the society, organization, group etc while in the word of Beckley (2009), status is the current state of something, the position or rank in relation to others. According to Franklin (2006) status is the particular condition that someone or something is at a specific time. From the above definitions, the word status can be said to be the current state of something or its position or state of affairs at a particular time. Status as used in this study denotes lecturers and students of business education in Nigeria universities. The lecturers and students are to determine extent of availability ICT resources for quality assurance.

Ownership of institution is another factor that may determine the availability of ICT resource in universities. There are many universities ownership in Nigeria ranging

from federal, state and private individuals or groups which may determine the funding, provision of resources and quality of services rendered. Bassey, Umoren, Akuegwu, Udida and Akpama (2007) noted that the academic staff in federal universities fared better than state academic staff in their job performance including the use of ICT. Supporting this view, Akuegwu, Ntukidem, Ntukidem and Jaja (2011) found that federal universities utilizes ICT facilities more than state universities due to funding. He further buttressed that federal universities are more funded than state universities. It is on the basis of the above varied opinions as regard gender, status and ownership of universities in relation to provision of ICT resources that the researcher deemed it fit to consider the significant level of these three variables to see their influences on the opinion of the respondents. Therefore, this study set to determine the extent of availability of ICT resources for quality assurance in business education in South-West Nigeria.

2. ICT in Business Education

ICT has the potential to transform the way education is delivered and promotes new opportunities therefore, enhancing scholarship and enquiries. This can only be attained when teachers, who are still the key to learning, have developed and utilized the necessary pedagogical competencies for instructional delivery through ICT resource utilization. Jones (2003) opined that effective learning is dependent on the will and competencies of the teacher in instructional delivery of lessons. This implies that teachers must undergo capacity building in ICT resources at the university level of education to enable them utilize maximally its benefit in instructional delivery.

Furthermore, ICT resources are instructional delivery tools used to explore, investigate, solve problems, interact, reflect reason and learn concepts in the classroom. This innovation permits alternative types of educational patterns for facilitating the teaching/learning process (Umoren, 2003). She conceptualized the ICT resources as the e-learning which is most commonly associated with higher education and corporate training that uses an information network through the internet, an intranet (LAN) or extranet (WAN). Electronic learning (e-learning) is used both in informal and formal educational setting for facilitation, instruction, interaction and for instructional delivery. Web-based learning is also a subset of e-learning. Another type of ICT resources is the virtual teaching which entails instructional delivery through teleconferencing the videoconferencing technique. Web based instruction uses internet and the World Wide Web (WWW) as the major component of learning materials and instructional resources for effective instructional delivery. Audio media (instructional slides and tutorials) are

teaching/learning aids made and written into compact disks, graphics and texts. Through the power point, instructional delivery is impactful to slow and fast learners. The need to assess the availability of ICT resources utilized for qualitative teaching and learning in business education in universities in South-West Nigeria has informed this research work.

2.1 Related Empirical Studies

The efficacy of ICT in higher education has been proved beyond reasonable doubt. It has been known to enhance educational opportunities of individuals and groups constrained from attending traditional universities as well as the use of computers as tutors for drills and practice as well as instructional delivery (Potashnik & Capper, 1998 and Font, 2002, in Umoren 2006). The unfortunate thing is that, ICT resources are beyond the reach of teacher educators and as such, they cannot access them for the purpose instructional development. Oviawe and Oshio (2011) conducted a study on impact of ICT on teaching and learning ability of education students in universities in Edo State, Nigera. The purpose of the study were to find out if ICT facilities were available for teaching and learning in teacher education programmes in universities in Edo State of Nigeria. Two research questions were used for the study and descriptive survey design was adopted. The population consisted of 128 teacher educators, questionnaire was the instrument used for data collection while simple percentage and chi-square statistics were used for data analysis. The major findings of the study showed that ICT facilities were not available to aid the teaching and learning of education students and boost their performance. Recommendations include that university authorities should acquire these ICT facilities in order to empower and meet the information needs of teacher educators and their students among other.

Similarly, Tella (2011) conducted a study on availability and use of ICT in south-western Nigerian colleges of education, with the purpose of examining the extent of availability and usage of ICT resources. Two research questions were used for the study and survey method was adopted. The population was made of 200 respondents and questionnaire was used while data were analyzed with simple percentage. The study revealed non-availability of some ICT equipment and that lecturers have not been sensitized enough to take advantage of ICT on teaching, learning, and research, some of the lecturers are unwilling to be resourceful while some await the college management sponsor them to training to use ICT. It was however, recommended ICT facilities should be adequately provided and that tutors should make effective use of hardware such ICT resources for teaching and learning effectiveness. These findings have been made elsewhere but not in universities in South-West Nigeria. The researcher then set

out to see the extent to which ICT resources are available for quality assurance of Business Education in South-West Nigeria.

2.2 Statement of the Problem

A cursory look at the tertiary institutions in Nigeria has shown that many lecturers in the system still rely much on the traditional lecture method of teaching rather than embracing the use of ICT. The stage of enlightenment in which ICT could be accessed and utilized in education is still low. Many lecturers hardly accessed and utilize the benefit of ICT in teacher education. Okebukola (1997) observed that computers, smart board, data projector, digital camera, etc are not adequately available and are being much less utilized, therefore they are not part of classroom technology in most tertiary institutions in Nigeria, and thus the lecture method and course materials / handout continue to dominate classroom activities. This is an indication that the students are still lagging behind in the trend of changes in the world of ICTs. This presupposes that there is the tendency for the students and teachers to be denied the opportunities which ICT offers in the teaching-learning activities. It is high time to place the traditional pedagogical practices that still underpin the educational system in this country, hence the call for the application of ICT in education system (Adekomi, 2006). Beside, many Nigerian teachers have been unable to find effective ways to utilize ICTs in their content delivery or any other aspect of their teaching due to non-availability of ICT resources (Ololube, 2006)

Moreover, as knowledge explorers, lecturers must as a matter of necessity be abreast with current ingestions, research network and innovations in instruction and instructional development. This knowledge can only be enhanced through availability and adequate utilization of ICT resources which will also lead to quality instructional delivery among lecturers. It is obvious that there are few studies that have looked at this phenomenon. Most of these studies were undertaken in colleges of education or at the university level. Therefore, there is need for a study on this sector of Nigerian education in order to ascertain the feelings or opinions of students and teachers on ICT resources availability as it relates to quality assurance in business education. The utilization of ICT resources in content delivery is still a mirage in Nigeria; hence the need to gain an insight on the available of ICT resources in business education.

2.4 Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to determine the extent of availability ICT resources for quality assurance in business education programme of universities in South-West Nigeria. Specifically, the study will determine the respondents' opinions and extent to

which ICT resources are available for quality assurance of business education programme in universities in South-West Nigeria.

2.5 Research Question

In the opinion of lecturers and students, to what extent:

1. Are ICT resources available for quality assurance in business education programme of universities in South-West Nigeria?

2.6 Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Male and female respondents do not differ significantly in their mean ratings on the extent ICT resources are available for quality assurance of business education programme in universities in South- West Nigeria.
2. Lecturers and students do not differ significantly in their mean rating on the extent ICT resources are available for quality assurance of business education programme in universities in South-West Nigeria.
3. Respondent do not differ significantly in their mean ratings on the extent ICT resources are available for quality assurance of business education programme in universities in South-West Nigeria based on institution ownership (federal/state).

3. Method

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population for this study consists of 550 (52 lecturers and 498 final year students) of business education from all Universities in South-West Nigeria. The choice of final year students is based on the fact that they have being in university system for more than three academic sessions and can easily form an opinion on any issue relating to their course of study. Sample for the study was 301 (52 lectures and 249 final year students) of business education from universities in the area of study. All the lecturers were used because of the size while stratified random sampling technique was used to select 50 percent of the students from each university that offers business education programme in the South-West Nigeria (Ekiti, Lagos and Ogun states). Instrument used for data collection was a validated five point rating scale questionnaire with a total of 18 items according to the research questions guiding the study. The reliability of the instrument was established through the use of Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Coefficient and reliability coefficients of 0.87 was obtained. Arithmetic mean was used to analyze data while the standard deviation was used to ascertain the homogeneity or otherwise of the respondents'

rating. Z-test was used to analyze data in respect of the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. A null hypothesis was accepted where the calculated z-value is less than the z-critical value but not accepted where the calculated z-value is equal to or greater than the z-critical value.

4. Results

To what extent are ICT resources available for quality assurance of business education programme in universities in south-west Nigeria?

Analysis of data in respect of research Question 1 is presented in Table 2. Analysis of data in respect of research Question 1 is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Respondents' mean ratings and standard deviation on adequacy of available ICT resources for quality assurance in business education

N = 301

S/N	Items on adequacy of available ICT resources	Lecturers		Students		Average		Remark
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
1	Departmental computers	3.85	0.69	3.86	0.73	3.86	0.72	High Extent
2	Internet connection facilities	1.69	0.83	1.76	0.89	1.75	0.88	Low Extent
3	Computer networking (Local Area Network)	1.50	0.61	1.42	0.59	1.43	0.59	Very Low Extent
4	Computer Networking (Wide Area Network)	1.29	0.54	1.36	0.58	1.35	0.57	Very low Extent
5	Multimedia projectors	3.35	0.71	3.32	0.71	3.33	0.71	Moderate Extent
6	Internet connection to all business education class	1.59	0.66	1.52	0.67	1.54	0.66	Low Extent
7	E-learning software packages	1.56	0.64	1.57	0.66	1.56	0.66	Low Extent
8	Examination scoring machine(OMR)	1.38	0.56	1.33	0.56	1.34	0.56	Very Low Extent
9	Multi-media classrooms (Audio Visual Centre)	1.73	0.76	1.74	0.77	1.74	0.77	Low Extent
10	Departmental website	1.59	0.63	1.67	0.67	1.66	0.66	Low Extent
11	Accounting education software packages	1.77	0.73	1.75	0.69	1.75	0.69	Low Extent
12	Office management education software packages	1.94	0.63	1.89	0.71	1.90	0.69	Low Extent

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13	Marketing/Distributive education software	1.36	0.66	1.34	0.65	1.35	0.65	Very Low Extent
14	Computer Screen Reading Software	1.67	0.47	1.58	0.49	1.60	0.49	Low Extent
15	Interactive white board	1.56	0.78	1.60	0.81	1.59	0.80	Low Extent
16	Institutional websites	4.25	0.62	4.24	0.63	4.24	0.62	High Extent
17	Still Digital Camera	1.42	0.57	1.46	0.59	1.45	0.59	Very Low Extent
18	Video Recorder	1.81	0.71	1.80	0.76	1.80	0.74	Low Extent
Cluster mean						1.96		Low Extent

Data in Table 1 show that only two of the eighteen ICT resources listed (1 and 16) are available in the university at a high extent while rest are available at a low and very low extent. The cluster mean of 1.96 indicate that ICT resources are available in the university and business education department to a low extent. The standard deviations for all the items range between 0.49-0.80 showing that the respondents were homogeneous in their opinions.

Null Hypothesis 1

Male and female respondents do not differ significantly in their mean ratings on the extent of qICT resources are available for quality assurance of business education programme in universities in South-West Nigeria.

Table 2: Z-test analysis of the difference between male and female respondents' mean ratings on the extent ICT resources are available

N = 301								
Gender	N	Mean	SD	z-cal	Alpha Sig.	Df	z-crit	Remark
Mal	151	34.86	3.53					
				0.33	0.05	299	1.96	NS
Female	150	34.99	3.57					

Data in Table 2 show a calculated z-value of 0.33 which is less than z-critical value of 1.96 at 299 degree of freedom and 0.05 level of significance. This means that respondents did not differ significantly in their mean rating on the extent ICT resources are available for quality assurance in business education programme in universities in South-West Nigeria. The null hypothesis was, therefore, upheld.

Null Hypothesis 2

Lecturers and students do not differ significantly in their mean rating on the extent of ICT resources availability for quality assurance of business education programme in universities in South-West Nigeria.

Table 3: Z-test analysis of the difference between lecturers and students mean ratings on the extent ICT resources are available

N = 301								
Status	N	Mean	SD	z-cal	Alpha Sig.	Df	z-crit	Remark
Lecturers	52	35.04	3.48	0.50	0.05	299	1.96	NS
Students	249	34.90	3.56					

Data in Table 3 show a calculated z-value of 0.50 which is less than z-critical value of 1.96 at 299 degree of freedom and 0.05 level of significance. This means that respondents did not differ significantly in their mean rating on the extent ICT resources are available for quality assurance in business education programme in universities in South-West Nigeria. The null hypothesis was, therefore, upheld.

Null Hypothesis 3

Respondents do not differ significantly in their mean ratings on the extent of ICT resources availability for quality assurance of business education programme in universities in South-West Nigeria based on institution ownership (federal/state).

Table 4: Z-test analysis of the difference between federal and state owned institution respondents mean ratings on the extent of ICT resources are available

N = 301								
Institutions ownership	N	Mean	SD	z-cal	Alpha Sig.	Df	z-crit	Remark
Federal	56	36.79	5.68	2.32	0.05	299	1.96	S
State	245	34.96	3.56					

Data in Table 4 show a calculated z-value of 2.32 which is greater than z-critical value of 1.96 at 299 degree of freedom and 0.05 level of significance. This means that respondents differ significantly in their mean rating on the extent ICT resources are available for quality assurance in business education programme in universities in South-West Nigeria. The null hypothesis was, therefore, not upheld.

5. Summary of findings

The following were the findings of the study: ICT resources are available at a low extent in universities for quality assurance in business education programme of universities in south-west Nigeria. Also, respondents differ significantly in their mean rating on the extent of ICT resources available for quality assurance of business education programme in universities in south-west Nigeria based on status and institutions ownership (federal/state), but did not as a result of gender.

6. Discussion of results

Findings of this study show that ICT resources are available for quality assurance in business education programme of universities in South-West Nigeria at a low extent. This finding is in agreement with that of Oviawe and Oshio (2011); Tella (2011); Akuegwu, Ntukidem, Ntukidem and Jaja, (2011); Jude and Dankaro, (2012) and Ajuzie and Akukwe, (2015). Specifically, Oviawe and Oshio (2011) reported that ICT facilities were not available in universities in Edo State except for telephone while Adedeji (2011) reported that less than 25% of colleges of education in South-West were provided with ICT resources for instructional delivery. Akuegwu, Ntukidem, Ntukidem and Jaja (2011) found that availability of ICT facilities for quality instructional delivery in universities in Akwa Ibom and Cross River States was significantly low except for internet-connected computers and institutional cybercafé. Jude and Dankaro (2012) found that ICT resources were not available in colleges of education in Kastina-Ala. While, Ajuzie and Akukwe (2015) reported that few ICT resources were available in the department of business education in Alvan Ikoku College of education, Owerri. This means that in spite of the popularity of ICTs, their low integration into the education system over the years has not changed because they are not adequately available.

Furthermore, findings of the study indicated that male and female respondents did not differ significantly in their mean ratings on the availability of ICT resources for quality assurance in business education in universities in South-West Nigeria. This finding is in conformity with those of Jude and Dankaro (2012) and Ajuzie and Akukwe (2015) which state that gender did not significantly affect the means of their respondents, that few ICT resources were available in the department of business education in Colleges of education in Nigeria. The findings also showed that lecturers and students did not differ significantly in their mean ratings on the extent ICT resources are available for quality assurance in business education in the universities in the area of study. This finding is similar to that of Asogwe (2007) and Major (2013)

Etoneyeaku, Kanu, Ezeji and, Chukwuma, (2014) who reported that there was no significant difference in the mean ratings of lecturers and students on availability of ICT resources.

However, the findings of the study revealed that respondents differed significantly in mean rating on the extent ICT resources were available for quality assurance in business education programme of universities in the area of study based on institution ownership (federal/State). This finding is in contrary to that of Okoro (2013) who found that there was no significant difference between mean ratings of federal and state universities respondents regarding the availability of office instructional resources in secretarial administration courses. This could be based on the fact that federal universities are more funded in terms of finance and supply of equipments including ICT resources than state owned universities.

7. Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it is concluded that ICT resources are not adequately available for quality assurance in business education programme of the universities in South-West Nigeria.

8. Recommendations

The following recommendations are suggested for policy options:

1. University management should make ICT resources adequately available for business education programme to enable their utilization by lecturer sand students for quality teaching and learning.
2. Universities management should enter into partnership with ICT manufacturing organizations to assist in improving the supply of the resources for their academic programmes towards quality assurance.
3. Government at the federal and state level should prioritize the funding of education sector to meet up with the recommendation of UNESCO and ensure adequate procurement of ICT resources for effective educational activities in universities.

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